

Comparative Evaluation of Hyaluronic Acid and Chlorhexidine on Postoperative Healing After Surgical Removal of Impacted Mandibular Third Molars

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Received: Feb 15, 2026

Accepted: Mar 13, 2026

Published: Mar 16, 2026

Abstract

Background: Impacted mandibular third molar extraction is one of the most common oral surgical procedures and is frequently associated with postoperative pain, inflammation, and periodontal complications affecting the adjacent second molar. Various adjunctive agents such as chlorhexidine and hyaluronic acid have been used to enhance wound healing and reduce postoperative morbidity.

Aim: To compare the effectiveness of chlorhexidine and hyaluronic acid in improving postoperative healing and reducing pain and periodontal pocket depth following surgical extraction of impacted mandibular third molars.

Methods: A comparative clinical study was conducted among 22 participants undergoing mandibular third molar surgery. Participants were randomly allocated into two groups: Study Group and Control Group of 11 each. Demographic and clinical characteristics were recorded. Postoperative outcomes were evaluated using Visual Analog Scale for pain, Verbal Rating Scale, and periodontal pocket depth measurements at baseline and on follow-up days (Day 1, 7 and 15). Descriptive statistics were calculated, and intergroup comparisons were performed using independent sample t-tests. Within-group changes over time were assessed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey HSD post-hoc tests.

Results: Both groups demonstrated progressive improvements in pain scores and periodontal parameters over the study period. In the study group, mean VAS scores decreased less compared to the control group. Similar reductions were observed in VRS scores and periodontal pocket depth. Significant within-group improvements were observed across all time points. However, a significant difference between groups was observed for VAS on Day 15.

Conclusion: Both chlorhexidine and hyaluronic acid were effective in improving postoperative healing and reducing pain following mandibular third molar surgery. However, chlorhexidine demonstrated more consistent outcomes, suggesting it remains a reliable and predictable option for routine postoperative management.

Keyword: Third molar; Impacted tooth; Chlorhexidine; Hyaluronic Acid; Postoperative Pain

Introduction

Oral diseases affect nearly 3.5 billion people worldwide which is close to 50% world's population, estimates the Global oral health status report of World Health Organization (2022). (1)

Third molars represent almost 90% of all dental impactions, mandibular third molars being the most frequently impacted teeth. At present, surgical extraction of MITMs is the most common procedure in oral surgery. Surgical indications include infection, affectation of adjacent teeth, orthodontic reasons, prosthodontic and restorative reasons, periodontal problems, mandibular angle fracture or risk of fracture, when the ITM impedes the correct development of reconstructive or orthognathic surgery, for patients who are to undergo radiotherapy of the head and neck, nervous events, and cystic-tumour complications. The NICE's clinical indications for the removal of ITM were cellulitis, abscess, osteomyelitis, and when this tooth is involved in or within the field of tumour resection. Oral wounds need longer time to heal completely due to a dynamic environment of the mouth in which healing occurs in warm oral fluid containing a high microorganism load and continued physical activity. (1) Postoperative complications include pain, inflammation, infection, trismus, prolonged bleeding, alveolitis osteitis or dry socket, sensory alterations of the inferior alveolar nerve or lingual nerve as also emphysema, paralysis of the facial nerve, pneumothorax, pneumo-mediastinitis, and pneumo-pericarditis. To reduce the incidence of complications, clinical and drug-based methods have been investigated such as cryotherapy; low-level laser therapy; numerous drugs and active intra-alveolar pharmaceuticals such as analgesics and/ or anti-inflammatories, platelet-rich fibrin, chitosan, 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHL), and 1% hyaluronic acid (HA). (2)

Chlorhexidine is considered a gold standard because of its property of substantivity. (3) Chlorhexidine digluconate is a broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent that has a marked effect on Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. (1,4) It has been shown to have both bacteriostatic and bactericidal activity, at a low (0.02-0.06%) and a high concentration (0.12-0.20%). (2,5,6) Chlorhexidine is also used as a local drug delivery agent. The use of CHX has been extended in postoperative periods to prevent plaque formation and early bacterial re-colonization of the treated area. (5) Drawbacks of CHX, including tooth discoloration and emerging antimicrobial resistance, allergy, epithelial desquamation, changes in taste and pigmentation of intraoral surfaces have spurred interest in natural alternatives such as hyaluronic acid (HA), aloe vera, and diode laser therapy. (3,4,6,7)

HA is biocompatible and intrinsically safe to use, with no evidence of cytotoxicity. (4) Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a high molecular weight polysaccharide that belongs to the family of glycosaminoglycans. (4,8) Hyaluronic acid or hyaluronan is essential in wound healing, facilitating cell migration and differentiation during tissue repair, and showing angiogenetic and osteoinductive effects. (1-5,7) Hyaluronic acid has an extensive action in various periodontal therapies such as topical application in

subgingival regions resulting in reduction of microbial activity, bone regeneration in deep periodontal bony defects, and nonsurgical treatment of peri implantitis pockets. (4) Its bacteriostatic characteristics are produced mainly at high concentrations ($\geq 0.8\%$). (2) HA exhibits anti-inflammatory, anti-oedematous, and antibacterial properties and modulates periodontal biofilm and immune responses. (1,3,6–8) HA has healing and regenerative properties. By reducing bacterial contamination of the surgical wound site, a therapeutic application of hyaluronic acid preparations during surgical therapy may lower the risk of postsurgical infection and promote healing following periodontal procedures. (1,2,4,5,7) Hyaluronan is further involved in the activation of inflammatory cells, such as polymorphonuclear leukocytes and macrophage functions, including their migration to the wound site, adherence at the wound site, phagocytosis killing of invading microbial pathogens in order to counteract the colonization and proliferation of anaerobic pathogenic bacteria in the gingival crevice and adjacent periodontal tissues. HA has been investigated as a drug delivery agent through topical route or through sub gingival irrigation. (4)

Results

Participant Characteristics

A total of 22 participants were enrolled, with 11 allocated to the Study Group and 11 to the Control Group. The mean age was 29.73 years (SD = 6.89) in the Study Group and 31.09 years (SD = 9.88) in the Control Group, with no statistically significant difference between the two ($t = -0.38$, $p = 0.711$).

Gender distribution was identical across groups, with males comprising 36.4% and females 63.6% in both groups (Table 1).

With respect to the second molar tooth, caries was present in 36.4% of the Study Group and 27.3% of the Control Group. Sensitivity was reported in 36.4% of the Study Group compared to 9.1% in the Control Group.

In terms of impaction type, the Study Group exhibited predominantly mesioangular impactions (36.4%), followed by horizontal (27.3%), distoangular (27.3%), and vertical (9.1%). In the Control Group, mesioangular impactions were more frequent (63.6%), followed by horizontal (18.2%), distoangular (9.1%), and inverted (9.1%).

Table 1. Frequency distribution of categorical variables

Variable	Category	Study Group n (%)	Control Group n (%)
Gender	Male	4 (36.4)	4 (36.4)
	Female	7 (63.6)	7 (63.6)
Caries w.r.t. tooth 7	Yes	4 (36.4)	3 (27.3)
	No	7 (63.6)	8 (72.7)
Sensitivity	Present	4 (36.4)	1 (9.1)
	Absent	7 (63.6)	10 (90.9)
Impaction	Mesioangular	4 (36.4)	7 (63.6)
	Vertical	1 (9.1)	0 (0)
	Horizontal	3 (27.3)	2 (18.2)
	Distoangular	3 (27.3)	1 (9.1)
	Inverted	0 (0)	1 (9.1)

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics for continuous variables are summarised in Table 2.

In the Study Group, mean VAS scores declined from 5.45 (SD = 2.02) on Day 1 to 0.55 (SD = 0.69) on Day 15. VRS scores decreased from 2.55 (SD = 1.04) to 0.27 (SD = 0.47), while follow-up pocket depth reduced from 4.36 mm (SD = 1.03) to 1.64 mm (SD = 1.29) over the same period.

In the Control Group, mean VAS scores fell from 5.09 (SD = 1.81) on Day 1 to 0.00 (SD = 0.00) on Day 15. VRS scores dropped from 1.91 (SD = 0.94) to 0.00 (SD = 0.00), and pocket depth decreased from 3.73 mm (SD = 1.49) to 1.36 mm (SD = 0.67).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for continuous variables

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD	Range
Age	Study	11	29.73	6.89	18
	Control	11	31.09	9.88	32
VAS Day 1	Study	11	5.45	2.02	7
	Control	11	5.09	1.81	6
VAS Day 7	Study	11	2.45	1.63	5
	Control	11	2.55	1.57	5
VAS Day 15	Study	11	0.55	0.69	2
	Control	11	0.00	0.00	0
VRS Day 1	Study	11	2.55	1.04	3
	Control	11	1.91	0.94	2
VRS Day 7	Study	11	1.09	0.83	3
	Control	11	0.64	0.50	1
VRS Day 15	Study	11	0.27	0.47	1
	Control	11	0.00	0.00	0
Pocket depth Day 1	Study	11	4.36	1.03	3
	Control	11	3.73	1.49	6
Pocket depth Day 7	Study	11	2.64	1.69	5

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD	Range
	Control	11	2.73	1.56	6
Pocket depth Day 15	Study	11	1.64	1.29	4
	Control	11	1.36	0.67	2

Between-Group Comparisons (Independent Samples t-test)

No statistically significant differences were observed between groups for age ($p = 0.711$), VAS scores on Day 1 ($p = 0.661$) or Day 7 ($p = 0.896$), VRS scores on Day 1 ($p = 0.148$), Day 7 ($p = 0.137$), or Day 15 ($p = 0.067$).

However, a significant difference was found for VAS scores on Day 15 ($t = 2.63$, $p = 0.016$), with the Study Group showing higher mean scores (0.55) compared to the Control Group (0.00). Levene's test indicated unequal variances for VAS Day 15 ($p < 0.001$) and VRS Day 15 ($p < 0.001$); however, results were consistent regardless of whether equal or unequal variances were assumed.

Within-Group Comparisons (One-Way ANOVA with Post Hoc Tests)

One-way ANOVA demonstrated statistically significant changes over time (Days 1, 7, 15) in both groups for VAS, VRS, and follow-up pocket depth measurements (all $p < 0.001$). Tukey HSD post hoc analysis identified distinct subsets for most time points, confirming progressive and statistically significant improvements within each group over the study period.

Discussion

Zodade A et al in 2025 designed a study to analyse and compare the antimicrobial activity of aloe vera, CHX, HA, and diode laser treatment against periodontal pathogens over varying in vitro exposure times (0.5, 1, 2, and 5 minutes). The key focus was to determine their effectiveness in inhibiting periodontal pathogenic bacteria. The mixed-methods study on 25 patients with chronic periodontitis. Subgingival plaque was collected from four quadrants per patient and randomized into four experimental groups (n = 25): 100% aloe vera gel, 0.2% CHX mouthwash, 10% dilution of 0.8% high-molecular-weight HA (1.5 MDa), and a 980 nm diode laser. Viable colonies were counted on blood agar plates after 48 hours incubation. The saline control (0.9%). Data were log-transformed and analysed. The 980 nm diode laser exhibited superior antibacterial efficacy for acute periodontal interventions, followed by CHX, HA, and aloe vera. These findings support the tailored use of adjunctive therapies based on exposure time and clinical needs for chronic periodontitis management. (6) Similarly, in the current study, chlorhexidine showed better results compared to hyaluronic acid on gingival healing and plaque status of the subjects.

Karale A et al in 2025 contemplated to evaluate and compare the efficacy of mouthwash containing chlorhexidine digluconate and chlorhexidine digluconate in combination with hyaluronic acid on post-operative healing after periodontal flap surgery on 30 subjects. Pocket depth reduction for chlorhexidine digluconate was significantly higher than that for the group with chlorhexidine digluconate in combination with hyaluronic acid 1-month post-operation. The intergroup comparison of reduction in pocket depth between the groups was statistically significant. (5) In the present study, the pocket depth reduction between groups was not significant throughout the study duration. However, there was a significant reduction in the pocket depth though the study duration within the groups.

Mendes VL in 2025 conducted a study aimed to evaluate the effect of three different CHX-based commercially available products on the subgingival microbial composition and metabolic activity using a multispecies biofilm model. The multispecies biofilm was treated with CHX 0.2%, CHX 0.2% + CPC, CHX 0.2% +HA 1%, and culture medium. The metabolic activity of the multispecies biofilm was measured using a spectrophotometric assay and the microbial composition by checkerboard DNA-DNA hybridization. The CHX+CPC gel was more effective than the other treatments in reducing proportions of red complex species and increasing bacterial species associated with periodontal health, A reduction of over half was observed in the microbial metabolic activity of biofilms treated with CHX and CHX + CPC, and a fourth in biofilms treated with CHX+HA. The CHX+CPC gel seems to have a superior antibacterial potential when compared to a gel containing CHX only, or CHX+HA, in an in vitro multispecies biofilm model. (3) This is not in accordance to the findings of the current study where hyaluronic acid performed worse than chlorhexidine.

In the current study, chlorhexidine with hyaluronic acid was found to be effective in reducing VAS, not significantly different from chlorhexidine. Similarly, Mittal T et al in 2025 compared and evaluated the effectiveness in terms of pain perception and soft tissue healing in patients treated with Hyaluronic acid and Chlorobutanol along with 0.20% Chlorhexidine as a subgingival irrigation following periodontal flap surgery. The result obtained from the study showed that subgingival irrigation with chlorobutanol and hyaluronic acid with 0.20% chlorhexidine positively influence the soft tissue healing and post operative pain after periodontal surgery. Curaspet can be used as an adjunctive treatment for improvement in wound healing process and reduction in post-operative pain. (4)

Shah H et al in 2024 intended to evaluate and establish the test product as a potential aid in faster wound healing and improving overall gum health in patients of post oral surgical procedures. In addition, the safety and acceptability of the mouth rinse was also evaluated. The test product was found significantly more effective than the placebo in aiding wound healing of oral surgical procedures. It also aided in improving overall gum health and reduced the post-operative pain, inflammation and teeth staining and can be recommended as an adjuvant to the patients of oral post-surgical procedures. (1) As against this, the current study noted chlorhexidine to be better option, though not significant. This difference is attributed to the fact that the control group in the study was Shah H et al was a negative control as against a positive control in the present study.

Shehatta et al in 2022 aimed to evaluate and compare the antibacterial efficacy of chlorhexidine and hyaluronic acid mouthwash on *Streptococcus viridans*. The study noted that Chlorhexidine at 0.2% concentration showed significant reductions of CFUs/ml. Hyaluronic acid did not have an effect on the number of colonies in all concentrations. Hyaluronic acid did not exhibit any antimicrobial effect on *Streptococcus Viridans*. (7) Similarly in 2020, Binshabib M et al aimed to present in-vitro study was to assess antimicrobial efficacy of 0.8% hyaluronic acid (HA) and 0.2% Chlorhexidine gluconate (CHX) against *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (*P. gingivalis*). The study concluded in-vitro; 0.8% HA is more effective in reducing the *P. gingivalis* CFUs/ml compared with 0.2% CHX. (8) In the current study too, there test group was not effective anti-gingivitis compared to the control group.

In 2021, Monoz-Camara D et al conducted a double-blind randomized control trial to analyse the postoperative effects of intra-alveolar applications of 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHL) or 1% hyaluronic (HA) acid bio-adhesive gels following the extraction of mandibular impacted third molars (MITMs). Visual analogue scales (VAS) were used to assess postoperative pain. 0.2% CHL and 1% HA bio-adhesive gels applied intra-alveolarly minimize the postoperative complications after MITM extraction. (2) In 2024, Boccalari E et al conducted a study to investigate the potential beneficial role of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and hyaluronic acid (HA) combination formulation in socket healing after third molar surgery concludes that the combination of hydrogen peroxide and hyaluronic acid can be considered a

potential mouthwash with beneficial effects on socket healing following third molar surgery. (9) In the current study, a significant difference was found for VAS scores on Day 15, with the chlorhexidine and hyaluronic acid group showing higher scores compared to the chlorhexidine group. Levene's test indicated unequal variances for VAS Day 15 and VRS Day 15. There were statistically significant changes over time in both groups for VAS and follow-up pocket depth measurements. Post hoc analysis identified distinct subsets for most time points, progressive and statistically significant improvements within each group over the study period.

The objective of a pilot study by Cardoso RR et al in 2020 was to evaluate the adjuvant effect of a mouthwash containing green tea and hyaluronic acid on peri-implant clinical parameters in users of full-arch implant-supported fixed prostheses on 11 patients with a total of 75 implants supporting 6 lower complete fixed prostheses and 7 upper complete fixed prostheses. The newly developed mouthwash proved to be safe for use, with no signs of negative side effects. Biofilm and inflammation index were reduced, with changes in the marginal level of the peri-implant mucosa due to reduced inflammation. The study concluded that the mouthwash containing green tea and hyaluronic acid successfully reduced biofilm accumulation and inflammation around dental implants in full-arch implant-supported fixed prostheses safely in a short-term evaluation period. (10) Similarly, the current study did prove that addition of hyaluronic acid to chlorhexidine did prove to be effective in improving the gingival and plaque health of the individual.

Trombelli L et al conducted a triple-blind, parallel-arm, randomized controlled trial in 2018 to evaluate the post-surgery gingival healing as well as plaque, gingival inflammation and staining levels following the use of a 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHX) solution with or without anti-discoloration system (ADS) and 0.2% hyaluronic acid (HA). Patients undergoing flap surgery at sites with an intact or reduced but healthy periodontium. After surgery, patients used the assigned mouthwash (CHX + HA + ADS or CHX) for 21 days. The study observations were similar to the current study stating post-surgery plaque control based on either CHX or CHX + HA + ADS mouthrinses results in optimal plaque control and quality of early gingival healing along with limited tooth and tongue staining. (11)

Conclusion

The present study compared the effectiveness of chlorhexidine and a combination of chlorhexidine with hyaluronic acid in improving postoperative outcomes following mandibular impacted third molar (MITM) extractions. Both groups demonstrated progressive and statistically significant reductions in pain, discomfort, and pocket depth over the 15-day follow-up period, confirming the beneficial role of adjuvant therapies in promoting wound healing and patient comfort. Intergroup comparisons, however, revealed no significant differences across most parameters, except for a higher VAS score on Day 15 in the study group, suggesting that chlorhexidine alone may offer slightly superior pain control at later stages of healing.

These findings align with previous literature that highlights chlorhexidine as the gold standard in managing postoperative plaque and gingival inflammation, while hyaluronic acid, although biocompatible and regenerative, did not provide additional clinical benefits when combined with chlorhexidine in this short-term evaluation. The results indicate that while both interventions are effective in enhancing gingival healing and reducing postoperative morbidity, chlorhexidine alone remains a reliable and more predictable option for routine use.

Nevertheless, the role of hyaluronic acid as an adjunct cannot be completely disregarded, as its long-term regenerative potential and anti-inflammatory properties warrant further exploration in larger, longer-duration clinical trials. Future research should also investigate varying concentrations, delivery systems, and combination therapies to better define the clinical value of hyaluronic acid in oral surgical wound management.

In summary, chlorhexidine continues to hold a superior position in the prevention of postoperative complications after third molar surgery, while hyaluronic acid, though safe and biologically advantageous, requires more robust evidence to establish its independent or synergistic clinical efficacy.

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